

Cancer and CAR-T Cells: the importance of these cells in the treatment of oncological diseases and their inclusion in the Unified Health System

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INTRODUCTION: Cancer is a term that defines more than 100 different types of disease that have in common the abnormal growth of cells. Dividing rapidly, these cells tend to be aggressive and uncontrollable, promoting the formation of tumors, which can spread to distant organs causing metastases. However, science has made progress in combating the disease with the help of high-tech therapies. Thus, in 1987, the first chimeric antigen receptor was created, and this treatment is already being used today and is proving to be effective and revolutionary. **OBJECTIVES:** To discuss the importance of CAR-T cell therapy in the treatment of oncological diseases and its adherence in the SUS. **METHODOLOGY:** This is an integrative literature review, with a reflective, descriptive and qualitative analysis. We used 6 articles from the journals: Nature and Biomedcentral (BMC); from the US government's cancer.gov website and from the Butantan Institute. **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:** This treatment has changed the view of cancer from a death sentence to something curable. The process of transforming CAR-T cells uses the patient's own immune system, beginning with a blood draw from the patient, where the blood goes through a T-lymphocyte separation stage. The T-lymphocytes receive the genetic material that provides the information needed to recognize membrane proteins that exist in cancer cells, causing them to become CAR-T cells, which in turn destroy abnormal cells. However, the challenge of this therapy is its high cost, as it is necessary to take the collection to countries that have the technology to separate the cells and apply the gene instructions. However, there is an urgent need to raise awareness of the importance, publicize and implement this therapy through the SUS, given that the principles of this health system are accessibility, resolvability and the integrity of care. Some progress has been made with the implementation of a research center at USP in partnership with the Butantan Institute and the Ribeirão Preto Blood Center. With this investment, the therapy should cost 5% of what it would cost to use imported inputs. **CONCLUSION:** It is understood that CAR-T is an innovative and effective treatment in the fight against cancer, but it requires financial and scientific investment in the area to favor the accessibility of this treatment to SUS users.

Keywords: Oncology; Therapeutics; Technology; Unified Health System.

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